

April 30, 2021

Perception of Farmers' Willingness to Pay for Learning in Taiwan

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Abstract

The increase of agricultural and food productivity is demanded for feeding the world's growing population. Extension education plays a crucial role in its improvement. Due to limited government expenditure to meet the need of further learning, farmers are requested to pay for their own extension education. The study analyzed animal farmers' willingness to pay for learning in Taiwan. Data were collected with a structured and validated questionnaire from 798 farmers. Data obtained from the questionnaires were analyzed using SAS. Results indicated that more than half of the respondents' work experience was above 6 years (57.4%), daily working time on animal farms was mainly 4-8 hours (41%), the majority were male (85%), and nearly one third (32%) were 25-34 years old. Two thirds of respondents' education levels (66.7%) were bachelor or graduate degree. Most respondents' (41.7%) incomes per month were NTD 20,000-40,000 (around USD 667-1,333). The majority of respondents were willing to pay for learning to improve knowledge and skills; only less than 8.8% of respondents were not willing to pay. They were willing to pay NTD 500-1,000 (around USD 17-33) for an 8-hour session per day, while for covering fees for materials or foreign experts, they were willing to pay NTD 1,001-2,000 (around USD 33-67). Those who would not pay for learning showed less motivation for learning activities. Surprisingly, compared with employers, employees would like to pay higher fees to improve their knowledge and skills. Interestingly, almost all respondents with higher education levels were willing to pay much more for learning activities. This research revealed that farmers had a willingness to pay for learning. Extension education should be provided for farmers to help them enhance their knowledge and skills, and maintain their competitiveness in the industry.

Key words: Animal production, Farmer, Learning, Willingness to pay, Extension education

INTRODUCTION

The increase of agricultural and food productivity is demanded for feeding the world's growing population. The improvement of quantity and quality in animal production relies on enhancing the use of modern technology and approaches. In times of rapid technological innovation and change, extension education plays a crucial role in this improvement. Everyone should have continuous learning to keep up with the pace of advanced knowledge and skills. This continuous learning or so-called lifelong learning includes formal learning for degrees, non-formal learning for non-degrees, and informal learning in daily life. The definition of purposeful learning can be found from the European Commission (CEC, 2000). Usually farmers' learning will pay particular attention to non-formal and informal learning, simply because of their lack of time for formal learning (Lans et al., 2004).

Traditionally, almost all public extension education for farmers has been free. Due to limited government expenditure to meet the need of learning, however, farmers are requested to pay for extension education. Some reports indicated a very high proportion were not willing to pay for extension services (Oladele, 2008; Onoh et al., 2014; Temesgen and Tola, 2015), while some reports indicated a vast majority of farmers were willing to pay for quality extension services (Bardhan, 2010), under the condition of guaranteed specific advice to increase profits for their farms (Temesgen and Tola, 2015), or improved access to extension services (Shee et al, 2020). However, information on animal farmers' willingness to pay for learning is uncommon in this country. Hence, this study was designed to:

1. Describe socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, and

April 30, 2021

2. Assess farmers' willingness to pay for learning activities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was an exploratory study, using a questionnaire approach. The subject of the questionnaire was to examine the willingness to pay for learning in the animal industry in Taiwan. During animal production conferences and training courses organized by the Animal Division of Innovation and Practical Training Center of National Pingtung University of Science and Technology, questionnaires were distributed to the participants to be completed. The survey responses were anonymous. A 6-point Likert scale was employed to determine opinions about willingness to pay for learning activities by farmers. Each question had six options, from 1 (indicating strongly disagree), 2, 3, 4, 5, to 6 (indicating strongly agree). Subjects gave single answers to better quantify the problem. Respondents were classified into two groups depending on their mean score. The mean scores above 3.5 were classified as positive, with those below as negative. Questionnaire data were analyzed using the general linear model procedure (GLM) in SAS (2004) for analysis of variance, and Duncan's new multiple range test used to compare differences among the means.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

A total of 1,388 questionnaires were issued and 838 were returned, for a recovery rate of 60.4%, of which 40 were voided due to more than half of the questions being unanswered; therefore, 798 questionnaires were accepted with an adjusted response rate of 57.5%.

The socio-economic characteristics of the respondents are given in Table 1. Respondents were mainly employees on animal farms (38.7%), while 29.1% were farm owners and owners' wives. This indicated that the majority of respondents were not decision makers of farm operations. In this study, the remaining respondents (31.3%) included technical persons, teachers, and students. They also actively participated in extension programs.

More than half of the respondents' work experience was above 6 years (57.4%). Only 13.8% were less than 1 year which meant they were new to this industry. Besides, most respondents had worked for quite a period of time, indicating that the industry was stable. The major respondents accumulated knowledge and skills through work experience, and they might have heard about or were required to pay for learning.

Respondents' daily working time on animal farms was mainly 4-8 hours (41%), followed by 9-12 hours (25.2%). Normal working hours are 8 hours per day in Taiwan. Those working less than 4 hours daily indicated part-time workers (15.2%), while the majority of respondents were full-time workers. Though part-time working is flexible, Pakistani researchers (Hashmi et al., 2016) concluded that full-time workers on cotton farms were more efficient than part-time workers. From the research results of Lee and Hsia (2020), respondents classified as working longer hours and those with more work experience had a much higher desire to learn. This indicated that the animal industry might be keen to support learning to increase efficiency in work.

Genders of respondents were male 85%, female 15%. This implied that animal farming was male dominated.

Nearly one-third (32%) of respondents were 25-34 years old, 23.7% were 35-44, and 21.5% were 45-54. This indicated that the animal industry still attracted the younger generations. Though only 3% of respondents were above 65, those aged persons were willing to attend relevant animal conferences or training courses. Lee and Hsia (2020) demonstrated that the learning motivation of respondents above 65 years old was frequently higher than those in the 15-24 year-old group. Though physical condition and cognitive function decline with age, older-aged farmers had a higher willingness to learn. Research conducted by Kimmel et al. (2016) indicated that students in the 24-or-under age group were found to be motivated to seek higher education due to their support from parents. Students in the 25-34 age group desiring a new career were among the motivations for seeking higher education. Students above 35 had several motivations including enrollment due to the desire for a pay increase, a new career, and more respect from peers.

April 30, 2021

Every respondent was educated. There was no illiteracy problem among the animal production workers. Two-thirds of respondents' education levels (66.7%) were university or graduate degree, which meant that most respondents were well educated and had already gained a certain amount of knowledge. Better educated farmers have the ability to manage farms well.

The average of most respondents' (41.7%) incomes per month was NTD 20,000-40,000 (around USD 667-1,333), followed by 24.3% at NTD 40,001-60,000 (around USD 1,333-2,000). Only 11.4% were paid lower than the minimum wage (NTD 20,000) as defined by the Ministry of Labor, ROC (Taiwan) in 2015. This indicated that most respondents had the ability to pay for learning.

Farmers' willingness to pay for learning activities

Through this survey, it was surprising to find that the majority of respondents were willing to pay for learning to improve knowledge and skills; only less than 8.8% of respondents were not willing to pay (Table 2). For learning activities which could improve professional skills or knowledge, excluding covering fees for medicine, materials, animals, or round-trip tickets and living expenses for a foreign expert, more than one third of respondents were willing to pay NTD 500-1,000 (about USD 17-33) for an 8-hour course per day. If the learning activity should cover the fees mentioned above, respondents were willing to pay NTD 1,001-2,000 (about USD 33-67) for an 8-hour course per day.

The relationships between pay-for-learning to improve skills and learning desire are given in Table 3. To improve professional skills, respondents who would pay above NT 2000 (around USD 67) for an 8-hour course per day (excluding costs of medicine, materials, or animals) expressed higher motivation for non-formal learning activities, reaching a significant difference ($P < 0.05$). They thought that attending a 5-day practical training session, attending 1-3 conferences per year, and inviting experts to farms were necessary; taking university courses and computer-assisted distance learning were helpful. Those who would not pay for learning showed less motivation for learning activities. It might be they lacked the time or financial support, or they thought they were encountering fewer problems, so they were less agreeable to training or attending conferences. They had fewer reference books. They also lacked proficiency in computer literacy, so were less agreeable to distance learning and searching the Internet in Chinese. As for low mean scores on looking for answers in libraries or bookstores, this might have been due to very few accessible professional libraries or bookstores. Mean scores for all groups were below 3.5 on items of encountering fewer problems in work and searching the Internet in English to resolve problems. This meant they agreed they had problems in work, but due to language barriers, they would seek other assistance or channels to find solutions. Results from Shee et al. (2020) indicated that improved access to extension services positively affected farmers' willingness to pay. They suggested that strengthening extension services could be a suitable policy intervention to increase farmers' demand for improved technologies.

Table 4 shows different participants' willingness to pay for learning. Normally, employers, including owners and owners' wives, should be more economically well-off and should be willing to pay much more to learn. However, the actual situation is different. Concerning any learning activities to improve professional skills or knowledge, owners' wives always showed the least willingness to pay; owners had almost the same opinion. This might be they were too busy running their businesses or thought non-formal learning was not necessary, and so tried to reduce costs and save money for their farms. On the contrary, compared with employers, employees were willing to pay higher fees to improve their knowledge and skills. This might be due to employers investing in themselves only to enhance competency for a better future, while employers invested everything in their farms to remain competitive in their industry so they cared about every expenditure. For technical persons, teachers, and students (others in the Table 4), they were used to paying for learning and knew the costs to have hands-on training and inviting foreign experts, so they were willing to pay much more for these learning activities.

Table 5 indicated the willingness to pay for learning among different education levels. Interestingly, almost all respondents with higher education levels were willing to pay much more for learning activities. This might be because they were acquainted and experienced with fixed charges when pursuing higher degrees; consequently, they accepted paying more for learning activities. Some data demonstrated that the highly educated tend to participate more in learning activities (Hamil-Luker and Uhlenberg, 2002; Alfageme, 2007;

April 30, 2021

Villar and Celdrán, 2013). Some researchers concluded that farmers with an agricultural college or university degree would seek professional assistance, use extension services, and use formal or informal sources of information (Fearne and Ritson, 1989; Corcoran and Dent, 1994; Bryden, 1997). Those with lower education levels might not have sufficient funds to learn, or lack reading comprehension and proficiency in computer literacy, so had less willingness to pay more for learning.

CONCLUSIONS

This research showed that the farmers had a willingness to pay for learning. The acceptable, affordable cost was NTD 500-1,000 (about USD 17-33) for an 8-hour course per day. If the learning activity should also cover the fees of materials or foreign experts, they were willing to pay NTD 1,001-2,000 (about USD 33-67) for an 8-hour course per day. Those who would not pay for learning showed less motivation for learning activities. Surprisingly, compared with employers, employees accepted paying higher fees to improve their knowledge and skills. Interestingly, almost all respondents with higher education levels were willing to pay much more for learning activities. Extension education should be provided for farmers especially for those with lower education levels to help them enhance their knowledge and skills, and maintain their competitiveness in the industry.

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April 30, 2021

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April 30, 2021

Table 1 Socio-economic characteristics of the respondents

Socio-economic characteristics	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Identity	Owner of farm	197	24.7
	Owner's wife	35	4.4
	Employee	309	38.7
	Other	250	31.3
	Missing data	7	0.9
	Total	798	100
Years of working experience	Less than 1 year	110	13.8
	1~3 years	145	18.2
	4~6 years	62	7.7
	Above 6 years	458	57.4
	Missing data	23	2.9
	Total	798	100
Working hours per day	Less than 4 hours	121	15.2
	4~8 hours	327	41.0
	9~12 hours	201	25.2
	Above 12 hours	50	6.2
	Missing data	99	12.4
	Total	798	100
Gender	Male	675	84.6
	Female	122	15.3
	Missing data	1	0.1
	Total	798	100
Age	15~24 years old	52	6.5
	25~34 years old	255	32.0
	35~44 years old	189	23.7
	45~54 years old	169	21.2
	55~64 years old	105	13.1
	65 years old and above	24	3.0
	Missing data	4	0.5
	Total	798	100
Education	Primary school	13	1.6
	Junior high school	39	4.9
	Senior high school	207	25.9
	University	299	37.5
	Graduate and above	233	29.2
	Missing data	7	0.9
	Total	798	100
Salary per month (NTD)	Less than 20,000	91	11.4
	20,000~40,000	333	41.7
	40,001~60,000	194	24.3
	Above 60,000	120	15.1
	Missing data	60	7.5
	Total	798	100

April 30, 2021

Table 2 Analysis of willingness to pay for learning

Willingness to pay	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Willing to pay for 8-hour course per day to improve professional skills (excluding the costs for medicine, materials, animals)	0	70	8.8
	Less than NTD500	167	20.9
	NTD500-1,000	293	36.7
	NTD1,001-1,500	111	13.9
	NTD1,501-2,000	72	9.0
	Above NTD2,000	42	5.3
	Missing data	43	5.4
	Total	798	100
Willing to pay for 8-hour course per day to improve professional knowledge (excluding the costs of round-trip tickets and living allowance for a foreign expert)	0	58	7.3
	Less than NTD500	151	18.9
	NTD500-1,000	312	39.1
	NTD1,001-1,500	129	16.2
	NTD1,501-2,000	57	7.1
	Above NTD2,000	46	5.8
	Missing data	45	5.6
	Total	798	100
Willing to pay for 8-hour course per day to improve professional skills (including the costs for medicine, materials, animals)	0	40	5.0
	Less than NTD1,000	237	29.7
	NTD1,001-2,000	287	36.0
	NTD2,001-3,000	121	15.2
	NTD3,001-5,000	45	5.6
	Above NTD5,000	26	3.2
	Missing data	42	5.3
	Total	798	100
Willing to pay for 8-hour course per day to improve professional knowledge (including the costs of round-trip tickets and living allowance for a foreign expert)	0	44	5.5
	Less than NTD1,000	189	23.7
	NTD1,001-2,000	253	31.7
	NTD2,001-3,000	169	21.2
	NTD3,001-5,000	74	9.3
	Above NTD5,000	21	2.6
	Missing data	48	6.0
	Total	798	100

April 30, 2021

Table 3 Relationship between pay-for-learning (medicine, materials, or animals not required) and learning desire, based on a six-point Likert scale

	0 元	500 元	500 ~	1,000 ~	1,500 ~	2,000 元	SEM	Sig.
		以下	1,000 元	1,500 元	2,000 元	以上		
Attending 5-day field training is necessary	4.24 ^b	4.49 ^{ab}	4.64 ^{ab}	4.46 ^{ab}	4.71 ^{ab}	4.96 ^a	0.18	*
Attending 1-3 conferences per year is necessary	4.82 ^c	5.28 ^b	5.17 ^{bc}	5.42 ^{ab}	5.27 ^b	5.79 ^a	0.14	*
Inviting professionals to farm is necessary	4.31 ^b	4.63 ^{ab}	4.78 ^{ab}	5.13 ^a	4.96 ^a	5.16 ^a	0.18	*
Taking courses in university is helpful (non-degree)	4.56 ^{ab}	4.53 ^{ab}	4.70 ^{ab}	4.69 ^{ab}	4.46 ^b	5.04 ^a	0.17	*
Distance learning through computer is helpful	3.77 ^b	4.42 ^a	4.49 ^a	4.29 ^a	4.32 ^a	4.60 ^a	0.17	*
Spending at least 2 hours per week to read books	4.56 ^b	4.85 ^{ab}	4.98 ^{ab}	5.21 ^a	5.05 ^a	5.16 ^a	0.14	*
Reviewing course after seminar or training course	4.95	4.83	4.82	5.16	4.86	5.13	0.14	NS
Reviewing course at night during training period	4.21	4.35	4.38	4.47	4.46	4.36	0.16	NS
Searching for information to resolve problems	5.18	5.21	5.25	5.26	5.16	5.52	0.13	NS
Encountering fewer problems in work	3.36	3.45	3.24	3.25	3.16	3.12	0.19	NS
Discussing with friends first to resolve problems	4.77 ^{ab}	4.64 ^{ab}	4.70 ^a	4.97 ^a	4.39 ^b	4.64 ^{ab}	0.16	*
Reading textbooks first to resolve problems	4.67 ^a	4.45 ^{ab}	4.52 ^{ab}	4.62 ^a	4.64 ^a	4.12 ^b	0.16	*
Reading magazines first to resolve problems	4.05	3.95	4.05	4.03	4.14	3.60	0.18	NS
Looking for experts first to resolve problems	4.69	4.95	4.95	4.84	4.68	5.00	0.16	NS
Thinking first to resolve problems	4.90 ^a	4.61 ^{ab}	4.63 ^{ab}	4.50 ^{ab}	4.32 ^b	4.96 ^a	0.17	*
Having at least 5 reference books (not magazines)	3.74 ^b	4.38 ^a	4.50 ^a	4.57 ^a	4.34 ^a	3.76 ^b	0.19	*
Having at least 1 magazine on animal production	4.39	4.67	4.74	4.86	4.30	4.64	0.22	NS
Searching Internet in Chinese to resolve problems	4.46	4.50	4.78	4.65	4.64	4.80	0.19	NS
Searching Internet in English to resolve problems	2.44 ^{ab}	2.27 ^b	2.90 ^{ab}	2.97 ^a	2.74 ^{ab}	2.72 ^{ab}	0.20	*
Looking for answers in library or bookstore	2.91 ^c	3.25 ^{abc}	3.51 ^{abc}	3.87 ^a	3.80 ^{ab}	3.20 ^{bc}	0.21	*

^{a-c}: Means within the same row without the same superscripts differ significantly

SEM: Standard error of mean

Sig.: NS: P > 0.05; *: P < 0.05

Table 4 Willingness to pay for learning from different positions of animal production workers

	Owner	Owner's wife	Employee	Others	SEM	Sig.
To improve professional skills, how much are you willing to pay for 8 hours per day (excluding the costs for medicine, materials, animals)? (1= NT0; 2= Less than NT500; 3= NT500-1000; 4= NT1001-1500; 5= NT1501-2000; 6= Above NT2000)	3.09 ^a	2.45 ^b	3.19 ^a	3.10 ^a	0.15	*
To improve professional knowledge, how much are you willing to pay for 8 hours per day (excluding the costs for round-trip tickets and living allowance for a foreign expert)? (1= NT0; 2= Less than NT500; 3= NT500-1000; 4= NT1001-1500; 5= NT1501-2000; 6= Above NT2000)	3.13 ^a	2.59 ^b	3.31 ^a	3.11 ^a	0.15	*
To improve professional skills, how much are you willing to pay for 8 hours per day (including the costs for medicine, materials, animals)? (1= NT0; 2= Less than NT1000; 3= NT1000-2000; 4= NT2001-3000; 5= NT3001-5000; 6= Above NT5000)	2.81 ^a	2.36 ^b	3.13 ^a	3.14 ^a	0.14	*
To improve professional knowledge, how much are you willing to pay for 8 hours per day (including the costs for round-trip tickets and living allowance for a foreign expert)? (1= NT0; 2= Less than NT1000; 3= NT1000-2000; 4= NT2001-3000; 5= NT3001-5000; 6= Above NT5000)	2.99 ^{ab}	2.62 ^b	3.19 ^a	3.39 ^a	0.14	*

^{a, b}: Means within the same row without the same superscripts differ significantly

SEM: Standard error of mean

Sig.: *: P < 0.05

Table 5 Willingness to pay for learning from different educational backgrounds of animal production workers

	Primary school	Junior high school	Senior high school	University	Graduate and above	SEM	Sig.
To improve professional skills, how much are you willing to pay for 8 hours per day (excluding the costs for medicine, materials, animals)? (1= NT0; 2= Less than NT500; 3= NT500-1000; 4= NT1001-1500; 5= NT1501-2000; 6= Above NT2000)	1.75 ^b	2.71 ^a	3.03 ^a	3.04 ^a	3.39 ^a	0.30	*
To improve professional knowledge, how much are you willing to pay for 8 hours per day (excluding the costs for round-trip tickets and living allowance for a foreign expert)? (1= NT0; 2= Less than NT500; 3= NT500-1000; 4= NT1001-1500; 5= NT1501-2000; 6= Above NT2000)	1.83 ^b	2.93 ^a	3.17 ^a	3.12 ^a	3.36 ^a	0.25	**
To improve professional skills, how much are you willing to pay for 8 hours per day (including the costs for medicine, materials, animals)? (1= NT0; 2= Less than NT1000; 3= NT1000-2000; 4= NT2001-3000; 5= NT3001-5000; 6= Above NT5000)	2.33 ^b	2.68 ^{ab}	2.86 ^{ab}	3.01 ^b	3.23 ^a	0.23	*
To improve professional knowledge, how much are you willing to pay for 8 hours per day (including the costs for round-trip tickets and living allowance for a foreign expert)? (1= NT0; 2= Less than NT1000; 3= NT1000-2000; 4= NT2001-3000; 5= NT3001-5000; 6= Above NT5000)	2.33 ^b	2.81 ^{ab}	2.93 ^{ab}	3.18 ^a	3.44 ^a	0.24	*

^{a, b}: Means within the same row without the same superscripts differ significantly

SEM: Standard error of mean

Sig.: *: P < 0.05; **: P < 0.01